

Table 1. Ingredients and proximate composition (%) of the experimental diets (CTR - control, BF1 – fortified diet B1, BF2 - fortified diet B2) for gilthead seabream (*S. aurata*) and common carp (*C. carpio*).

Ingredients (%)	Gilthead seabream			Common carp		
	CTR	BF1	BF2	CTR	BF1	BF2
Fishmeal 70 ¹	15.0	10.0	10.0	-	-	-
Fishmeal 60 ²	-	-	-	5.00	2.50	2.50
Fish protein concentrate ³	2.50	2.50	2.50	-	-	-
Porcine blood meal ⁴	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.00	2.00	2.00
Algae meal (<i>Tetraselmis</i> sp.) ⁵	-	0.50	0.50	-	-	-
Algae meal (<i>Spirulina</i> sp.) ⁶	-	-	-	-	1.00	1.00
Algae meal (<i>Chlorella</i> sp.) ⁷	-	5.00	5.00	-	1.00	1.00
Algae meal (<i>Schizochytrium</i> sp.) ⁸	-	3.20	3.20	-	1.56	-
Soy protein concentrate ⁹	17.0	17.0	17.0	2.50	2.50	2.50
Corn gluten meal ¹⁰	8.00	8.00	8.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
Soybean meal 48 ¹¹	8.00	8.00	8.00	-	-	-
Soybean meal 44 ¹²	-	-	-	25.0	25.0	25.0
Rapeseed meal ¹³	-	-	-	7.00	7.00	7.00
Sunflower meal ¹⁴	-	-	-	12.5	12.5	12.5
Corn meal ¹⁵	-	-	-	2.50	2.50	2.50
Wheat meal ¹⁶	16.6	14.4	14.0	22.5	21.8	22.4
Wheat glúten ¹⁷	12.0	12.0	12.0	-	-	-
Wheat bran ¹⁸	-	-	-	5.00	5.00	5.00
Fish oil ¹⁹	5.45	4.36	5.45	-	-	-
Salmon oil ²⁰	-	-	-	-	-	2.10
Soybean oil ²¹	2.81	2.49	2.16	3.00	-	2.00
Rapeseed oil ²¹	5.61	4.98	4.32	3.00	5.10	2.00
Linseed oil ²¹	0.94	0.83	0.72	-	-	-
Vitamins and minerals premix ²²	1.10	1.10	1.10	1.00	1.00	1.00
Betaine HCl ²³	-	-	-	0.10	0.10	0.10
Binder ²⁴	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Macroalgae meal (<i>Laminaria digitata</i>) ²⁵	-	0.40	0.80	-	0.54	0.54
Antioxidant ²⁶	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Sodium propionate ²⁷	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
Monoammonium phosphate ²⁸	0.50	0.50	0.50	-	-	-
Sodium phosphate ²⁹	-	-	-	2.10	2.10	2.10
Selenised yeast ³⁰	-	0.02	0.04	-	0.01	0.01
L-Taurine ³¹	0.40	0.50	0.50	-	-	-
L-Tryptophan ³²	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.20	0.20	0.20
DL-Methionine ³³	0.20	0.30	0.30	0.60	0.60	0.60
L-Lysine ³⁴	-	-	-	0.70	0.70	0.70
Dry matter (DM), %	7.90 ± 0.00	8.10 ± 0.00	8.10 ± 0.01	5.30 ± 0.01	6.40 ± 0.02	8.30 ± 0.02
Crude protein, % DM	46.0 ± 0.1	45.7 ± 0.2	45.5 ± 0.1	30.2 ± 0.2	30.4 ± 0.1	30.3 ± 0.1
Crude fat, % DM	17.2 ± 0.1	17.3 ± 0.1	17.3 ± 0.1	8.10 ± 0.10	8.00 ± 0.10	8.10 ± 0.20
Ash, % DM	5.30 ± 0.00	5.30 ± 0.01	5.30 ± 0.01	4.40 ± 0.10	7.20 ± 0.20	7.20 ± 0.10
Iodine, mg kg ⁻¹ DM	1.24 ± 0.02	7.38 ± 0.66	13.3 ± 0.2	2.22 ± 0.03	16.3 ± 0.3	15.6 ± 0.3
Selenium, mg kg ⁻¹ DM	0.70 ± 0.00	1.05 ± 0.01	1.28 ± 0.02	0.40 ± 0.01	1.47 ± 0.05	1.41 ± 0.05

¹CONRESA 70: 47.4% crude protein (CP), 817.5% crude fat (CF), Conserveros Reunidos S.A., Spain; ²CONRESA 60: 61.2% crude protein (CP), 8.4% crude fat (CF), Conserveros Reunidos S.A., Spain; ³Porcine blood meal: 589% CP, 1% CF, SONAC BV, The Netherlands; ⁴Tetraselmis meal: 72% CP, 1% CF, Willows Ingredients Ltd, Ireland; ⁵Spirulina meal: 72% CP, 1% CF, Willows Ingredients Ltd, Ireland; ⁶Chlorella meal: 62% CP, 9% CF, ALLMICROALGAE, Portugal; ⁷ALL-G RICH (Schizochytrium), Alltech Portugal; ⁸Soycomil P: 63% CP, 0.8% CF, ADM, The Netherlands; ⁹Corn gluten meal: 61% CP, 6% CF, COPAM, Portugal; ¹⁰Solvent extracted soybean meal: 43.8% CP, 3.3% CF, CARGILL, Spain; ¹¹Solvent extracted soybean meal: 43.8% CP, 3.3% CF, CARGILL, Spain; ¹²Solvent extracted soybean meal: 43.8% CP, 3.3% CF, CARGILL, Spain; ¹³Defatted rapeseed meal: 32.7% CP, 4.1% CF, Ribeiro & Sousa Lda, Portugal; ¹⁴Defatted sunflower meal: 72.9% CP, 1.8% CF, Ribeiro & Sousa Lda, Portugal; ¹⁵Com meal: 8% CP, 3.7% CF, Ribeiro & Sousa Lda, Portugal; ¹⁶Wheat meal: 10.2% CP, 1.2% CF, Casa Lanchinha, Portugal; ¹⁷Wheat glúten; ¹⁸Wheat bran: 14.9% CP, 4.0% CF, Cerealis Moagens S.A., Portugal; ¹⁹Fish oil; ²⁰Sopropéche; ²¹Henry Lamotte Oils GmbH, Germany; ²²INVIVONSA Portugal SA, Portugal; Vitamins (IU or mg/kg diet): DL-alpha tocopherol acetate, 100 mg; sodium menadione bisulphate, 25mg; retinyl acetate, 20000 IU; DL-cholecalciferol, 2000 IU; thiamin, 30mg; riboflavin, 30mg; pyridoxine, 20mg; cyanocobalamin, 0.1mg; nicotinic acid, 200mg; folic acid, 15mg; ascorbic acid, 500mg; inositol, 500mg; biotin, 3mg; calcium panthotenate, 100mg; choline chloride, 1000mg; betaine, 500mg. Minerals (g or mg/kg diet): copper sulphate, 9mg; ferric sulphate, 6mg; potassium iodide, 0.5mg; manganese oxide, 9.6mg; sodium selenite, 0.01mg; zinc sulphate, 7.5mg; sodium chloride, 400mg; excipient wheat middling's; ²³ORFFA, The Netherlands; ²⁴CELATOM FP1SL (diatomite), Angelo Coimbra S.A., Portugal; ²⁵Dry Laminaria digitata: 5.4% CP, 0.5% CF, 3700 mg iodine/kg, Agrimer, France; ²⁶VERDILOX, Kemin Europe NV, Belgium; ²⁷PREMIX LDA., Portugal; ²⁸Vadequímica, Spain; ²⁹ALKOSEL R397: 2200 mg selenium/kg, Lallemand, France; ³⁰L-Taurine; ³¹TrpAMINO 98%, Evonik Nutrition & Care GmbH, Germany; ³²DL-METHIONINE FOR AQUACULTURE 99%, EVONIK Nutrition & Care GmbH, Germany; ³³L-Lysine HCl 99%: Ajinomoto Eurolysine SAS, France.

Table 2. Average certificate and measured concentrations ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry matter) and the associated relative standard deviation (RSD) in certified reference materials (CRM). Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) for each element and analytical method.

Elements	Analytical method	Type	CRM		LOD ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)
			Certificate value ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	Measured value ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)		
As	ICP-MS	ERM®-BB422	12.7 ± 0.7	12.0 ± 0.2	0.003	0.013
I*	ICP-MS	ERM®-BB422	1.40 ± 0.40	1.23 ± 0.02	0.010 (0.068)	0.036 (0.25)
Se	ICP-MS	ERM®-BB422	1.33 ± 0.13	1.21 ± 0.02	0.007	0.025
Cl	μ -EDXRF	SRM 1571	700	600 ± 100	100	-
K	μ -EDXRF	SRM 1571	14700 ± 300	13500 ± 1300	20	-
Ca	μ -EDXRF	SRM 1571	20900 ± 300	19500 ± 2000	30	-
Fe	μ -EDXRF	DORM-4	142 ± 10	150 ± 15	5	-
		SRM 1571	12 ± 1	13 ± 1		
Cu	μ -EDXRF	DORM-4	2.3 ± 0.2	2.4 ± 0.8	1	-
		SRM 1571	12 ± 1	13 ± 1		
Zn	μ -EDXRF	DORM-4	27 ± 2	28 ± 3	1	-
		SRM 1571	25 ± 3	24 ± 2		
Br	μ -EDXRF	SRM 1571	10	11 ± 1	1	-

*Iodine values for fish matrix and in parentheses for feed matrix

ICP-MS (Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer); μ -EDXRF (micro energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometry); ERM®-BB422 (Fish muscle CRM, Joint Research Centre (JRC), Brussels); SRM 1571 (Orchard leaf National Institute of Standards and Technology, EUA); DORM-4 (Fish Protein CRM, National Research Council of Canada, Canada).

Table 3. Concentrations of macro, trace and toxic elements and true retention (TR) of gilthead seabream (*S. aurata*) fed with different experimental diets (CTR - control, BF1 – fortified diet B1, BF2 - fortified diet B2)

	CTR			BF1		BF2		TR (%)
	Raw	Steam	TR (%)	Raw	Steam	Raw	Steam	
Macro elements (mg 100 g ⁻¹)								
Cl	444 ± 31 ^a	377 ± 8 ^A	73	477 ± 20 ^a	372 ± 5 ^{A*}	530 ± 33 ^b	461 ± 4 ^{B*}	73
K	1244 ± 24	1444 ± 163	100	1747 ± 371	1596 ± 57	1742 ± 150	1683 ± 148	81
Ca	70 ± 19 ^c	52 ± 3 ^{C*}	65	37 ± 6 ^b	25 ± 1 ^{B*}	12 ± 2 ^a	9.5 ± 0.1 ^A	65
Trace elements (mg kg ⁻¹)								
I	0.07 ± 0.00 ^a	0.10 ± 0.00 ^{A*}	125	0.07 ± 0.01 ^a	0.11 ± 0.00 ^{B*}	0.09 ± 0.00 ^b	0.12 ± 0.00 ^{C*}	110
Se	0.18 ± 0.00 ^a	0.18 ± 0.01 ^A	88	0.23 ± 0.01 ^b	0.23 ± 0.00 ^B	0.36 ± 0.01 ^c	0.40 ± 0.00 ^{C*}	93
Fe	7.1 ± 0.5 ^a	7.8 ± 0.6 ^A	95	12.1 ± 2.8 ^b	9.6 ± 0.6 ^A	29.0 ± 2.8 ^c	23.9 ± 3.4 ^{B*}	69
Cu	2.0 ± 0.0 ^b	<LOD [*]	n.d.	2.9 ± 0.6 ^c	<LOD [*]	<LOD ^a	<LOD	n.d.
Zn	1.0 ± 0.2 ^a	1.1 ± 0.0	93	1.6 ± 0.2 ^b	1.3 ± 0.0	0.9 ± 0.1 ^a	1.1 ± 0.2	106
Br	3.1 ± 0.2 ^b	<LOD [*]	n.d.	4.2 ± 0.2 ^c	<LOD [*]	<LOD ^a	<LOD	n.d.
Toxic elements (mg kg ⁻¹)								
As	1.8 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.1 ^B	91	1.5 ± 0.2	1.5 ± 0.0 ^A	1.5 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.0 ^A	87

Values are mean ± standard deviation, in wet weight. Different superscript small letters represent statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatments (CTR, BF1, BF2) in raw fish filets and different superscript capital letters represent statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatments in steamed fish filets. * represent statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between raw and steamed fish filets in each treatment. LOD – Detection limit

Table 4. Concentrations of macro, trace and toxic elements and true retention (TR) of common carp (*C. carpio*) fed with different experimental diets (CTR - control, BF1 – fortified diet B1, BF2 - fortified diet B2)

	CTR			BF1		BF2		TR (%)
	Raw	Steam	TR (%)	Raw	Steam	Raw	Steam	
Macro elements (mg 100 g⁻¹)								
Cl	92 ± 4	106 ± 5 ^{B*}	95	101 ± 11	148 ± 3 ^{C*}	84 ± 11	85 ± 9 ^A	81
K	902 ± 57	746 ± 26 [*]	68	918 ± 79	841 ± 51	900 ± 30	821 ± 17 [*]	73
Ca	126 ± 9 ^b	98 ± 25 ^{B*}	64	95 ± 26 ^b	75 ± 5 ^B	38 ± 1 ^a	30 ± 2 ^{A*}	63
Trace elements (mg kg⁻¹)								
I	<LOQ ^a	<LOQ ^A	n.d.	0.21 ± 0.02 ^b	0.23 ± 0.02 ^B	0.19 ± 0.00 ^b	0.21 ± 0.02 ^B	89
Se	0.09 ± 0.00 ^a	0.10 ± 0.01 ^A	87	0.14 ± 0.01 ^b	0.14 ± 0.01 ^B	0.14 ± 0.00 ^b	0.14 ± 0.00 ^B	80
Fe	14.7 ± 1.8	20.9 ± 2.5 ^{A*}	117	20.9 ± 4.6	23.4 ± 1.1 ^A	22.1 ± 5.4	35.2 ± 0.5 ^{B*}	128
Cu	8.0 ± 0.4 ^b	6.3 ± 0.0 ^{B*}	65	1.8 ± 0.4 ^a	1.6 ± 0.0 ^A	2.3 ± 0.5 ^a	2.1 ± 0.1 ^A	73
Zn	11.4 ± 1.2 ^a	12.7 ± 0.4 ^{A*}	91	13.8 ± 1.6 ^b	14.9 ± 0.9 ^B	13.7 ± 0.2 ^b	15.8 ± 0.2 ^{B*}	93
Br	4.8 ± 0.1 ^b	4.6 ± 0.3 ^B	79	1.9 ± 0.4 ^a	1.9 ± 0.1 ^A	2.7 ± 0.4 ^a	2.5 ± 0.0 ^A	73
Toxic elements (mg kg⁻¹)								
As	0.08 ± 0.00 ^a	0.07 ± 0.00 ^A	72	0.26 ± 0.02 ^b	0.19 ± 0.01 ^{B*}	0.27 ± 0.01 ^b	0.21 ± 0.00 ^{B*}	62

Values are mean ± standard deviation, in wet weight. Different superscript small letters represent statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatments (CTR, BF1, BF2) in raw fish fillets and different superscript capital letters represent statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatments in steamed fish fillets. * represent statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between raw and steamed fish fillets in each treatment. n.d., not determined. <LOQ, below the quantification limit.

Table 5. Nutritional contribution (%) of steamed gilthead seabream (*S. aurata*) and common carp (*C. carpio*) in terms of essential elements in different population groups, considering the consumption of a portion of 150 g of fish for adults and pregnant women, and with the consumption of 75 g of fish for children.

		DRVs (mg day ⁻¹) ⁴	Gilthead seabream			Common carp		
			CTR	BF1	BF2	CTR	BF1	BF2
Macro elements								
Cl	Adults ¹ /Pregnant women ²	AI 3100	18 ± 3	18 ± 0	22 ± 0	5 ± 0	7 ± 0	4 ± 0
	Children ³	AI 1700	17 ± 3	16 ± 0	20 ± 0	5 ± 0	7 ± 0	4 ± 0
K	Adults ¹	AI 3500	62 ± 7	68 ± 2	72 ± 6	32 ± 1	36 ± 2	35 ± 1
	Pregnant women ²	AI 4000	54 ± 6	60 ± 2	63 ± 6	28 ± 1	32 ± 2	31 ± 1
Ca	Children ³	AI 800	> 100	> 100	> 100	70 ± 2	79 ± 5	77 ± 2
	Adults ¹ /Pregnant women ²	AR 750	11 ± 1 ^b	5 ± 0 ^a	2 ± 0 ^a	20 ± 0 ^c	15 ± 1 ^b	6 ± 0 ^a
Trace elements	Children ³	AR 390	10 ± 1 ^b	5 ± 0 ^a	2 ± 0 ^a	19 ± 0 ^c	14 ± 1 ^b	6 ± 0 ^a
	Adults ¹	AI 0.15	10 ± 0 ^a	11 ± 0 ^b	12 ± 0 ^c	n.d. ^a	23 ± 2 ^b	21 ± 2 ^b
I	Pregnant women ²	AI 0.20	7 ± 0 ^a	8 ± 0 ^b	9 ± 0 ^c	n.d. ^a	17 ± 1 ^b	16 ± 1 ^b
	Children ³	AI 0.09	8 ± 0 ^a	9 ± 0 ^b	10 ± 0 ^c	n.d. ^a	19 ± 2 ^b	18 ± 1 ^b
Se	Adults ¹	AI 0.07	40 ± 1 ^a	50 ± 1 ^b	85 ± 2 ^c	21 ± 1 ^a	30 ± 2 ^b	30 ± 0 ^b
	Pregnant women ²	AI 0.085	33 ± 1 ^a	41 ± 0 ^b	70 ± 2 ^c	17 ± 1 ^a	25 ± 1 ^b	24 ± 0 ^b
Fe	Children ³	AI 0.015	92 ± 3	> 100 (29 ± 0)	> 100 (50 ± 1)	48 ± 3 ^a	71 ± 4 ^b	69 ± 0 ^b
	Adults ¹	AI 3.4	31 ± 2 ^a	54 ± 12 ^a	> 100 (8 ± 1) ^b	92 ± 10	> 100 (8 ± 0)	> 100 (12 ± 0)
Cu	Pregnant women ²	AI 2.9	37 ± 3 ^a	63 ± 15 ^a	> 100 (8 ± 1) ^b	> 100 (7 ± 1)	> 100 (8 ± 0)	> 100 (12 ± 0)
	Children ³	AI 0.6	98 ± 8	> 100 (2 ± 0)	> 100 (6 ± 1)	> 100 (5 ± 1)	> 100 (6 ± 0)	> 100 (9 ± 0)
Zn	Adults ¹	AI 1.6	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	59 ± 0 ^b	15 ± 0 ^a	20 ± 1 ^a
	Pregnant women ²	AI 1.5	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	63 ± 0 ^b	16 ± 0 ^a	21 ± 1 ^a
Zn	Children ³	AI 0.7	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	68 ± 0 ^b	18 ± 0 ^a	23 ± 1 ^a
	Adults ¹	AR 6.2	3 ± 0	3 ± 0	3 ± 1	31 ± 1 ^a	36 ± 2 ^{ab}	38 ± 1 ^b
Zn	Pregnant women ²	AR 8.6	2 ± 0	2 ± 0	2 ± 0	22 ± 1 ^a	26 ± 2 ^{ab}	28 ± 0 ^b
	Children ³	AR 3.6	2 ± 0	3 ± 0	2 ± 0	26 ± 1 ^a	31 ± 2 ^{ab}	33 ± 0 ^b

Values are mean ± standard deviation. The Nutritional contribution (NC; %) are presented for ¹adults (> 18 years) with mean body weight in Europe (70 kg), ²children (1–3 years) with mean body weight in Europe (13 kg) and ³pregnant/lactating women with mean body weights in Europe (67 kg) set by EFSA (2012). ⁴The Dietary Reference Values (DRVs) are presented as Adequate Intakes (AI) for I (EFSA, 2014a), Se (EFSA, 2014b), Fe (EFSA, 2015a), Cl (EFSA, 2015c), K (EFSA, 2016) and P (EFSA, 2019), as well as the tolerable upper intake level (UL; in parenthesis) and adequate requirement (AR) for Ca (EFSA, 2015b) and Zn (EFSA, 2014c). n.d., not determined due to contents below the detection limit (<LOD). No tolerable upper intake level (UL) has been set for K by EFSA due to insufficient data (EFSA, 2016). Different superscript small letters represent statistical differences (p < 0.05) between treatments (CTR, BF1, BF2). CTR – control; BF1 – fortified B1; BF2 – fortified B2.

Table S1. Gilthead seabream (*S. aurata*) and common carp (*C. carpio*) biometric information moisture (%) content before and after the feeding trial.

	<i>n</i>	Total length (cm)	Total weight (g)	Muscle fillet			CY (%)
				Moisture Raw (%)	Moisture Steam (%)	Weight loss (%)	
Gilthead seabream							
Baseline	15	31 ± 2	491 ± 68	69 ± 4 [#]	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
CTR	15	33 ± 1	549 ± 52	69 ± 1 [#]	68 ± 0 [#]	14 ± 2 [#]	86 ± 2 [#]
BF1	15	32 ± 1	517 ± 55	68 ± 0 [#]	68 ± 1	13 ± 2 [#]	87 ± 3 [#]
BF2	15	33 ± 2	525 ± 49	69 ± 1 [#]	68 ± 1 [#]	14 ± 2 [#]	84 ± 5 [#]
Common carp							
Baseline	15	29 ± 3	333 ± 44	78 ± 0 [§]	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
CTR	15	40 ± 2	1236 ± 108	75 ± 3 [§]	73 ± 1 [§]	19 ± 2 [§]	81 ± 2 [§]
BF1	15	39 ± 2	1138 ± 108	75 ± 1 [§]	70 ± 2 [§]	19 ± 2 [§]	81 ± 2 [§]
BF2	15	41 ± 2	1338 ± 112	76 ± 1 [§]	73 ± 0 ^{§,*}	20 ± 3 [§]	80 ± 3 [§]

n, number of specimens analysed; n.d., not determined; CY, cooking yield; CTR, control diet; BF1, fortified diet B1; BF2, fortified diet B2. The symbols (§, #) indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between species, whereas * represent statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between raw and steamed fish filets in each treatment.